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Modeling and Validation of IAEA 3D PWR Benchmark Problem Using COMSOL Multiphysics Code

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Abstract

A relevant challenge in nuclear reactor analysis is to achieve a broad description of nuclear systems through the coupling between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics. A multi-physics approach improves the reactor safety analysis and the design of different types of nuclear reactor phenomena where accurate modeling is essential for the integration of different physical effects at different scales of time and space. COMSOL Multiphysics software provides an advanced tool to integrate user-defined physics module to analyze reactor state at steady and transient state by mathematics module. To validate the capability of solving different nuclear reactor phenomena e.g., neutron flux distribution and effective multiplication factor in COMSOL software, it's worth solving a benchmark problem. The neutron diffusion equation is used widely in academia and in the industry to perform core-level neutronic calculations which consist of a set of second-order partial differential equations over the spatial coordinates. A classic 3D IAEA benchmark problem is solved for validation which is defined by B. Micheelsen in 1971 and the goal of this benchmark problem is to validate software capability with the help of neutron diffusion equation by calculating the multiplication factor, neutron flux, radial, and axial power distributions in the core. The 3D model has been built up using SolidWorks software and later model is imported into COMSOL to solve neutron diffusion equations for the 3D IAEA PWR benchmark problem. An adaptive meshing algorithm has been used to omit peculiarities that often arise when solving the neutron diffusion equation using unstructured grids. Effective multiplication factor " k_{eff} ", thermal and fast neutron flux profiles, and power distributions were calculated and compared to the results of another standard PARCS code. There is a good agreement between the results from COMSOL and PARCS code. The obtained neutron multiplication factor (k_{eff}) 1.02799 from COMSOL is consistent with the PARCS code in the benchmark at the level of 0.11%. This paper documents the use of the commercial finite element Multiphysics software package COMSOL 5.4 on a 3D benchmark problem for LWR.

Keywords: *CFD, COMSOL Multiphysics, K_{eff} , PWR, SolidWorks.*

1. Introduction

Neutronics behavior in different reactor models should be analyzed through the coupling of Multiphysics problems by different techniques to solve reactor problems and code must be validated through benchmark experimental data. The Boltzmann neutron transport equation describes how neutrons interact with matter and represents a balance of neutrons that holds at every point in space and at every instant in time. The neutron diffusion equation is a simplification of the Boltzmann neutron transport equation that states that the neutron current is proportional to the gradient

of the neutron flux. An IAEA 3D PWR, defined by B.Micheelsen in 1971 and later published in 1977 by the computational benchmark problems committee of the mathematics and computation division of the American Nuclear Society, the problem has been chosen in recent years as the benchmark problem for validating advanced neutronic and thermal-hydraulics codes and data libraries. In this paper, COMSOL Multiphysics has been adopted for validation with detailed specifications from the IAEA 3D benchmark problem. COMSOL is a powerful finite element-based computational program to model and predict different

represent source term. D is the diffusion coefficient and Σ_f is the macroscopic fission cross-section. The benchmark model consists of five different regions given in table 2.3 with cross-section data for fast and thermal groups respectively. Three boundary conditions are applied as symmetry boundary conditions (BC), vacuum BCs and continuity BCs.

For external boundaries, there is no incoming current as showing in eqⁿ (3)

$$j_g^{in} = 0 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Reflective boundaries with no net current as shown in eqⁿ (4)

$$\frac{\partial \phi_g}{\partial n} = \frac{0.4692}{D_g} \phi_g \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Simplified of above equation for using in COMSOL is eqⁿ (5)

$$\phi_{g|boundary} = -2.1312 D_g \nabla \phi_{g|boundary} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Simplified neutron diffusion equation is in non-linear form which is non-symmetric matrix. This problem can easily solve in eigenvalue mode.

$$-\lambda. \phi_1 - D_1 \nabla^2 \phi_1 + (\Sigma_{a1} + \Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}) \phi_1 = (\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1 + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2) \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

$$-\lambda. \phi_2 - D_2 \nabla^2 \phi_2 + \Sigma_{a2} \phi_2 = \Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2} \phi_1 \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Simplified neutron diffusion equation in COMSOL is in following form-

$$-\lambda \Delta u + \nabla \cdot (-d_g \nabla u) + \Sigma_r u = \Sigma_{f,g} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

Symmetry Neuman boundary condition is written in COMSOL in the form of

$$(-D \nabla \phi_g) = 0 \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

Dirichlet boundary condition is the value of variable at a certain point. Dirichlet boundary condition in reflective region where flux is vanished at extrapolated distance.

$$hu = r \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

The final condition is the continuity condition. Which is in the form of

$$n \cdot ((c \nabla u - \alpha u + \gamma)_1 - (c \nabla u - \alpha u + \gamma)_2) + qu = g \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

$$n \cdot ((D \nabla \phi)_1 - (D \nabla \phi)_2) = 0 \dots \dots \dots (12)$$

K_{eff} value is calculated by following equation-

$$\begin{aligned} k_{eff} &= [\iiint \Sigma_f^1 \phi^1 dv + \iiint \Sigma_f^2 \phi^2 dv]^{R1} \\ &+ [\iiint \Sigma_f^1 \phi^1 dv + \iiint \Sigma_f^2 \phi^2 dv]^{R2} \\ &+ [\iiint \Sigma_f^1 \phi^1 dv + \iiint \Sigma_f^2 \phi^2 dv]^{R3} \\ &+ [\iiint \Sigma_f^1 \phi^1 dv + \iiint \Sigma_f^2 \phi^2 dv]^{R4} \\ &+ [\iiint \Sigma_f^1 \phi^1 dv + \iiint \Sigma_f^2 \phi^2 dv]^{R5} \\ &- P_0 \dots \dots \dots (4.13) \end{aligned}$$

Here, R₁=Fuel 1

R₂= Fuel 1+ Rod

R₃=Fuel 2

R₄=Reflector

R₅= Reflector + Rod

Graphical User Interface of mesh in IAEA 3D PWR for one-quarter is given in following Figure (3).

Figure 3: 3D mesh generated by COMSOL Multiphysics

4. Result:

The value of K_{eff} calculated by using COMSOL Multiphysics for extremely fine meshes per assembly is 1.02799. The reference value of $K_{eff} = 1.029096$ which is calculated by PARCS code and error is 0.11%

Three-dimensional flux distribution in whole core is given in figure 4 and 5 respectively. In Y-Z plane 50 slice plot are taken to plot flux distribution quite density in whole core.

Figure 4: 3D plot of fast neutron flux

Figure 5: 2D plot of fast(left) and thermal(right) neutron flux at $z = 150$ cm

In fast neutron flux, maximum flux occurs in middle of core. Flux vanishes at extrapolate distance. Thermal neutron flux in middle plane shows flux is quite constant (no abrupt change or peak value of flux) except at radial direction in reflector region. Not all reflector periphery side shows this perturbation, only a certain location gives peak value of thermal flux distribution.

Line graph of fast and thermal neutron flux from figure 6 and 7 respectively gives details information how these value changes. An important point is that thermal flux makes a peak value at inner side of core. Boundary condition both fast and thermal neutron flux vanish at radial direction. At middle point, both thermal and fast flux makes a hump but not in same quantity. Fast flux value changes at a large amount because of partially rodded fuel assembly at mid plane.

Figure 6: Fast and thermal neutron flux at Y-Z plane.

Power at axial layer number is normalized over whole core. At middle point in axial direction power is maximum. Power distribution curve is Cosine-shape which is also agree with our theoretical concept. Power is decreasing at axial direction.

Figure 7: Axial power distribution.

Assembly power mainly comes from thermal, because of thermal flux peaking at radial direction, assembly power in those assembly unexpectedly large than reference value. Near the assemblies containing rods, which introduce larger gradient of flux and power values. Assembly power distribution for one-quarter geometry of IAEA 3D PWR are calculated by COMSOL Multiphysics which is given in figure 8.

0.72 0.87 -20.8%	1.27 1.4462 -13.39%	1.42 1.8204 -28.17%	1.18 1.6452 -20.98%	0.61 0.6452 -11.48%	0.95 1.033 -8.74%	0.96 0.99 -3.125%	0.78 0.85 -8.97%
1.27 1.4436 -13.67%	1.39 1.7732 -27.57%	1.42 1.00925 -28.925%	1.29 1.0058 22.03%	1.07 1.03099 3.65%	1.05 1.0048 4.3%	0.98 0.98 0%	0.76 0.87 -14.47%
1.42 1.81 -27.46%	1.42 2.01 -41.5%	1.36 0.99 29.41%	1.31 1.07 18.32%	1.18 1.0086 14.5%	1.08 1.28 18052%	1.00 1.0185 -1.85%	0.72 1.75 -43%
1.19 1.6312 -37.07%	1.29 1.9945 -35.02%	1.31 1.01 22.9%	1.18 1.002 15.08%	0.97 1.03 -6.19%	0.92 .09878 -6.52%	0.87 1.0243 -17.74%	
0.61 .02876 52.85%	1.07 0.81 24.3%	1.18 1.01 14.4%	0.97 1.028 -5.98%	0.48 0.7122 4.9%	0.7 1.04 -44.85%	0.62 0.85 -37.09%	
0.95 1.0309 -8.5%	1.05 0.9946 5.71%	1.08 1.00 8%	0.92 0.9895 -6.52%	0.7 1.05 50%	0.6 1.07 -6.78%		
0.96 0.99 -3.125%	0.98 0.9843 0.1%	1.00 1.023 -2.3%	0.87 1.039 -19.42%	0.62 0.867 39.4%			
0.77 0.8593 -11.6%	0.76 0.8802 -15.8%	0.72 0.8766 -21.11%					

Reference value (PARCS code)
Calculated value (COMSOL)
Error (%)

Figure 8: Power distribution in quarter core compared with reference value.

5. Conclusion:

3D PWR IAEA benchmark problem was modeled using COMSOL 5.4 in .mphbin file. k_{eff} is sensitive with different mesh quality. Adaptive mesh refinement is taken care of for accurate solution. Normalized power is in a good agreement with reference PARCS CODE except radial direction which is adjacent to reflector side. Thermal and Fast flux in one-quarter geometry also agree with our reference solution. The value of k_{eff} is 1.02799 which shows smaller difference of 0.11% with PARCS CODE. This power is normalized over whole geometry power. Reflector region shows a large discrepancy in flux value which effect on normalized power. Maximum error in assembly power is 52 %. Cosine shape power distribution in each assembly also well agree with theoretical concept.

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